

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.5 Final Dissemination and Communication (DC) Plan

Public

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1. Introduction

This document is part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package - WP6. The first Dissemination and Communication Plan (DC – Deliverable (D) 6.1) introduced the overall engagement approach that CYCLOPES is to follow throughout the project. The Plan was revised in M30 through Deliverable 6.3 Updated Dissemination and Communication Plan. This is the final update to the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

The DC Plan ensures efficient internal and external communications, as well as proper dissemination activities. The detailed plan explores a variety of audiences and their respective needs and special interests. This is to ensure that the targeted audiences will be apprised of the most pertinent results stemming from the project.

To fully capitalize on the project's achievements and maximize its benefits, audiences are encouraged to be actively involved with the project itself. This plan outlines the methods and key messages essential for effectively engaging relevant stakeholders, as well as how to maintain continuity of the relationship between them and the CYCLOPES consortium.

Furthermore, the DC Plan ensures that:

- Project outputs and outcomes are widely disseminated to the right target audiences, respecting an appropriate and defined timing, through intelligible channels and tools,
- Stakeholders can contribute to the outputs' development, evaluation and exploitation. Thus, they should be identified and encouraged from the start to proactively interact with the consortium partners on a systematic basis.

As the CYCLOPES project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) initiative, primarily focused on producing reports on practitioners' gaps and requirements, along with other deliverables that support Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) in combating cybercrime, it is evident that certain confidential reports are intended exclusively for consortium partners and relevant EU bodies and stakeholders. However, the CYCLOPES team will also provide condensed – redacted versions of certain reports to support the active dissemination within the wider community.

The project dissemination continues to focus on network extension and sharing of the results internally and among the identified stakeholders and audiences of interest. Thus, the project requires an understandable stakeholders' engagement approach - a key point of the DC. Furthermore, CYCLOPES intends to amplify the results and activities of other members of the cybercrime ecosystem – helping to maximise its impact and positive change in the fight against different forms of cybercrime.

The primary step of knowing what has to be reached and understanding why it must be reached, has helped with the implementation of the engagement process in a significant way. These efforts defined the appropriate messages for the relevant stakeholders, selected adequate tools and use of suitable channels, respecting a defined timing.

The key audiences for CYCLOPES, as described in the proposal documents are:

- Practitioners,
- Industry including SMEs,
- Scientific Community,
- Policy makers

The strategy also includes key messages and means of approaching the stakeholders.

Key updates to this DC plan are:

- Dissemination guidelines booklet to be created - a supportive guide for partners towards better dissemination of project results.
- collaboration with the Cyberspace LEA Cluster in the field of dissemination of project results and participation to joint events.
- Initiation of dissemination to relevant networks:
 - Ways are being explored to connect with the INTERPOL's Cybercrime Knowledge Exchange Workspace,
 - Access to CMINE network.
 - Extended communication and collaboration with Forensic Capability Network (UK)
- Video/Audio production update
- Reviewed the KPIs to reflect the observed performance indicators derived from the 2nd Midterm Project Dissemination Impact Assessment Report (Deliverable 6.4).
- Collaboration has been initiated with Sparks in the Dark community. The collaboration includes for example webinars and social media visibility.
- Updates to the overall content reflecting current dissemination objectives.

This document includes the following sections:

1. The first section indicates general initial dissemination and communication objectives.
2. The second section analyses dissemination and communication objectives.
3. The third section analyses engagement of the audiences in the cybercrime domain.
4. The fourth section focuses on identifying the target audiences.
5. The fifth section dwells into the key messages based on the output/input from/to the project.
6. The sixth section outlines the dissemination tools.
7. The seventh section presents the project communication strategy.
8. The eighth section provides KPIs on monitoring and assessment of the D&C.

2. Dissemination and Communication Objectives

In addition to the most common communication and dissemination activities such as the project web page, social media channels, policy briefs, newsletters, reports and so on, the D&C continues to be attained through the use of the following dissemination methods:

- participating in events dedicated to practitioners, industry and research – presenting the project's outcomes and encouraging exploitation of the results.
- directly sharing outcomes with identified EU projects developing tools and solutions for practitioners fighting cybercrime.
- developing bi-annual reports for the European Commission about CYCLOPES findings.
- annual reports for policymakers on European and national level, with recommendations of research areas which should be financed in the future.
- annual CYCLOPES dissemination workshops.

In terms of a specific methodological approach, the CYCLOPES project employs a methodology, which provides a 360-degree or continuous cycle approach consisting of planning, performing, assessing, and reporting (Figure 1).

Figure 1 CYCLOPES D&C, 360 degree - continuous cycle approach.

The CYCLOPES project comprehends the importance of communicating the project results, and for this reason, project implements thorough internal and external communication and dissemination activities.

The objectives for **CYCLOPES external communications and dissemination** are to:

- Ensure efficient dissemination of project results.
- Create project visibility.
- Reach various target groups (please refer to the following section 4).
- Guarantee sustainability of the project results (implemented through the Communication and Dissemination strategy).

- Increase the awareness about both the topic of cybercrime and cybersecurity and specific purposes and actions linked to the project.
- Involve the whole community in a participatory communication plan structured in various steps.

The objectives for **CYCLOPES internal communication and dissemination** are to:

- Monitor the status of CYCLOPES developments to keep WPs aware of the project progress.
- Ensure coherent internal communication between WPs.
- Make relevant internal information available also to external communication.
- Ensure an efficient and smooth communication among partners.
- Allow and enable the sharing of interesting and relevant content for the project.

DC Plan addresses the relevant stakeholders through several identified channels, which include the following:

- Social networks (X and LinkedIn);
- YouTube channel;
- Website;
- Webinars;
- Newsletter;
- Use of following information sharing platforms by partners (all or a select few):
 - Community of Users EC Platform,
 - ENLETS Community,
 - i-LEAnet project's platform,
 - iProcureNet project's platform,
 - CMINE Platform,
 - INTERPOL's CKE
 - EC CIRCABC
 - Forensic Capability Network
 - Stair4Security project's platform and so on
 - Europol's Platform for Experts
- Promotion of open science with selected public information, published in EC platforms such as:
 - European Open Science Cloud,
 - [CORDIS](#),
- Workshops and Exercises;
- Consortium partners' own networks;
- CYCLOPES' network members.

The above-mentioned tools and platforms are a few steps that the project incorporates to maximise its impact. More on those will follow in the sections below.

Furthermore, taking into account the significant amount of information processed by audiences' daily through various outlets i.e. social media, in order for CYCLOPES to maximise the effectiveness of communications, messages should focus on short, concise, to the point communications strategy. Such strategy could be beneficial when it comes to: newsletters, social media publishing and other similar outlets.

Given that CYCLOPES is a coordination and support action project, this could also be a limiting factor to some degree due to the intended audience being specific. Nevertheless, the follow

up of the DC Plan has tracked dissemination progress and provides additional direction and clarification to the activities according to the identified needs. Furthermore, communication and dissemination activities will be efficiently linked with exploitation activities of the project and the DC Plan is updated together with the Exploitation Plan (EP).

3. Engaging with targeted audiences in the cybercrime & cybersecurity domain

3.1. Objectives for engaging

Efficient dissemination during the CYCLOPES project ensures short and long-term success of the project. In any research or coordination project, the dissemination is a fundamental activity to create project visibility and reach various target groups. This is core to the strategy of spreading knowledge about the project among different target groups by using different instruments.

Understanding the reasoning behind stakeholders' engagement is the first step for a well-defined engagement strategy; including the selection of appropriate tools to be used. Below are five main objectives for engaging CYCLOPES stakeholders:

1. **Extend and enhance CYCLOPES' reputation:** communicating about CYCLOPES' aim, objectives and work that is dedicated to cybercrime prevention will improve its image and gain stakeholders' trust;
2. **Extend the network and cooperation** between LEAs in the cybercrime and cybersecurity domain.
3. **Gather information** about CYCLOPES stakeholders' needs and requirements.
4. **Boost awareness of CYCLOPES' objectives and outcomes** at local, national, European and international levels;
5. **Intensify CYCLOPES' impact:** efficient and personalised communication with stakeholders will support the uptake of the project's outcomes and increase their relevance.

3.2. Level of engagement

Like other EU funded projects, CYCLOPES follows the Spectrum of Public Participation which has been developed by the [International Association of Public Participation](#), which is to:

Inform: provide the CYCLOPES communities with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities, and/or solutions.

Consult: obtain feedback on analysis, alternatives, and/or decisions.

Engage: work directly with the community members throughout the project and beyond to ensure that practitioners' concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered.

Collaborate: partner with the CYCLOPES community members in each aspect of the decision-making process - including the development of alternative options and the identification of the preferred 'solutions'.

Empower: place final decision-making authority in the hands of the CYCLOPES community members.

More detailed information on how the project CYCLOPES adopts the above methodology can be found on the WP5's deliverable D5.1. *Community Building Framework and Governance model*. For this deliverable we will mainly focus on the dissemination perspective.

4. Identified stakeholders and target groups

To maximise the engagement of the stakeholders, the key point is to clearly define the categories of stakeholders, their needs and the priority group they belong.

In this document we are mainly focusing on identification of target groups and their needs for dissemination purposes in order not to duplicate efforts with WP5. WP5 will delve more into detail on the stakeholder engagement activities.

By engaging key stakeholders from the start of the project, CYCLOPES acquired a more motivated and interested participant base and allowed early opportunities for dissemination communication and exploitation. In addition, the targeted and timely communication allows the different target groups to be informed about and participate in the various events planned in the project.

When it comes to the identified stakeholders, the following questions are considered:

- Is there a need to disseminate and why?
- Who are the target audience?
- What is the content that is being disseminated?
- Who is completing the dissemination?
- When is dissemination taking place?
- How will it be disseminated?

Figure 2 CYCLOPES Stakeholder Audiences

The key stakeholders as defined in the project proposal are divided into four main categories (Figure 2):

4.1. Practitioners

With practitioners in the context of CYCLOPES project, it is referred to the Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs), interested in the uptake of security research and innovation in relation to the fight against cybercrime.

CYCLOPES partners will engage practitioners throughout the project timeframe by inviting relevant stakeholders to events and workshops, by proposing that they take part in different initiatives and ask for their feedback on how CYCLOPES solutions can support enhanced resilience to cybercrime.

CYCLOPES has requested to join the INTERPOL Cybercrime Knowledge Exchange (CKE) workspace and is currently waiting for a response. CKE workspace is open to law enforcement, governments, international organisations and cybersecurity industry experts to exchange non-police operational information on cybercrime. Currently the workspace has around 8000 members. Also, CYCLOPES collaborates actively with the Cyberspace LEA Cluster of projects, disseminating project results as well as participation to joint events. CYBERSPACE is managed by Privanova who also disseminates cluster results to the INTERPOL's CKE.

CYCLOPES has initiated talks with the Forensic Capability Network from the UK. The discussion is ongoing to find common interests for dissemination and event participation. The FCN works closely with LEAs in the field of forensics including digital forensics. This on itself presents an opportunity for the CYCLOPES project to increase outreach to LEA practitioners engaged in forensic investigations in the UK.

CYCLOPES thus far has identified the following networks/practitioners and is engaged in some form with several of them. Some of the agencies mentioned below are not fully classified as LEAs however, the main target are the LEAs participating in those networks, plus the actions that are providing results and outputs utilised by LEAs – such as EACTDA and ECTEG.

As the CYCLOPES network increased to include more LEAs, the list has expanded. A separate excel document holds a full list and is in possession of the WP5 leader.

Table 1 List of targeted practitioner audience

Practitioners community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>LEA full partners</i>	12 full project partners	
<i>Practitioners' Forum</i>	Additional EU LEAs,	Proactively disseminate information related to the project, formal invitations to join the network via several planned channels.
<i>Practitioners' Networks</i>	LEAs participating to the following networks: ENLETS, CYBERSPACE LEA Cluster STARLIGHT, ENFSI, ECTEG, i-LEAD, CERIS EU-HYBNET, ARCSAR, i-ProcureNet, POLARCLUSTER & POLARNET Forensic Capability Network NOTIONES Sparks in the Dark	Proactively disseminate information related to the project to increase visibility of project existence. Provide a project summary to include in their media. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to join the network via several planned channels. Join their networks.
<i>EU / international orgs</i>	LEAs from the following: EC3, Interpol, CEPOL, Europol Innovation Hub, ENISA EACTDA	Proactively disseminate information and reports related to the project. Provide a project summary to include in their media. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to join the network via several planned channels. Join their networks.

4.2. Industry including SMEs

When it comes to the industry and SMEs, it generally means those whose activities are relevant to cybercrime/cybersecurity. This includes:

- Manufacturers
- Service providers
- Vendors
- Industry Associations
- Suppliers
- Industry Think Tanks

CYCLOPES project has a dedicated work package 3 to conduct the market and research watch, as well as WP5 that focuses on stakeholder engagement. Nevertheless, all consortium members are expected to play a role in the engagement activities as well i.e. the industry with interests in cybercrime and work constructively with its wide network (security industry, suppliers of security solutions). It can be that some of the partners have own contacts or are members of other networks which they could invite to CYCLOPES activities, or at least make them known to the WP5 leader. This network has been and will continue to receive invitations to attend events, workshops and webinars of CYCLOPES and will receive all supportive documents needed to actively participate in key activities.

Certainly, the challenge to find and engage adequate industry SMEs with substantial interest to the project and willingness to contribute, is recognized and the project has been selective in this regard. There is a multitude of SMEs, many of which are either dealing with specific niche clients or some are very limited based on their representation on their websites.

Nevertheless, in order for the project to maximize its reach to the industry, CYCLOPES consortium is encouraged to participate to events, conferences, networks, clusters, fairs and so on where industry participation is high.

The following is a preliminary list of some of the potential Industry SMEs/networks that have been invited to contribute in CYCLOPES events. Worth to note that some of the SMEs chosen are coming from the project i-LEAD, where they were contributors to the project events.

Table 2 List of targeted audience from the industry/SMEs

Industry community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>Industry SME's</i>	All identified industry and SMEs	Proactively contact individual SME's to share project news and attract their interest to establish contacts and newsletter subscription as well as participate to CYCLOPES project events and vice versa.
Industry members of networks	Industry participating to the following networks: EUROPEAN Digital SME Alliance, NETWORLDEUROPE, ENFSI, ECTEG, i-LEAD, CERIS, EU-HYBNET, ARCSAR, i-ProcureNet NOTIONES	Proactively participate to events. Announce the project existence to the networks and include perhaps a short project bio in their website. Participate to the project clusters as well and show a badge of membership. Engage in social media and invite them to join to our events.
<i>EU / international orgs</i>	Industry/SMEs from the following: ECSO, CEEMET, SIINDA, UNIFE, Europol Innovation Hub, ENISA, SAFECLUSTER,	Proactively participate to events. Announce the project existence to the networks and include perhaps a short project bio in their website. Participate to the project clusters as well and show a badge of membership. Engage in social media and invite them to join to our events.

4.3. Scientific community

CYCLOPES results and updates will continue to be delivered to relevant EU and Member State organisations. There are several scientific communities identified at the beginning such as:

- Universities,
- Research and technology organisations,
- Research communities and institutes,
- The private sector.

Participation from this target group will be mutually beneficial. For CYCLOPES it means that an essential component in the development process is present in the project to contribute with experiences and input on feasibility of project results and much more. To the researchers, it provides means of tapping into a vast repository of knowledge related to topics such as cyber-physical threats, emergency response, forensics, cybercrime, information systems and system resilience.

Table 3 Preliminary list of potential target for scientific communities.

Practitioners community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>Scientific full CYCLOPES partners</i>	All	
<i>Scientific Forum</i>	All scientific forums identified	Proactively disseminate information related to the project, public reports, formal invitations to join project activities via several planned channels.
<i>Scientific' Networks</i>	Scientific members participating to the following networks: ENFSI, EU Research Gate ECTEG, i-LEAD, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET, ARCSAR, i-ProcureNet, POLARCLUSTER & POLARNET NOTIONES Sparks in the Dark	Proactively disseminate information related to the project to increase visibility of project existence. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to join the project activities via several planned channels.
<i>EU / international orgs</i>	Scientific communities from the following: Open Research Europe , European Open Science Cloud, Initiative for Science in Europe, Science Europe, EU Science Hub, CORDIS, EC Horizon Results Platform,	Proactively disseminate information and public reports related to the project. Provide a project summary to include in their media. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to participate to CYCLOPES activities via several planned channels. Join their networks.

4.4. Policymakers

Through policy-oriented partners, policy and decision makers have been approached. The CYCLOPES consortium identifies and proactively engages with targeted personnel and invites

interested actors to project events and workshops. The relevant files under discussion will also be identified and their development monitored by the consortium.

CYCLOPES continues to reach policymakers on a **European** (i.e. DG Home, DG Connect, DG Grow) and **National** level (member states).

These audiences are at the core of the main goals of the DC plan. Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient audience relations to enable interaction between differing innovation parties, and build synergies with already established European, national and sub-national networks of practitioners. Moreover, efficient communication and dissemination measures, together with exploitation activities, are the key in fulfilling the goals of the Work Program.

Table 4 Preliminary list of potential target Policymakers

Practitioners community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>Member State Level</i>	All project partners' national level policymakers. EU member national policymakers.	Proactively disseminate information related to the project, public reports, formal invitations to join project activities via several planned channels.
<i>EU /Global level</i>	DG HOME, DG CONNECT, DG GROW, DG MOVE, DG MARE, REA, EC, ENISA, CEN, CENELEC, ISO	Proactively disseminate project results. Extend formal invitations to participate to CYCLOPES activities via several planned channels. Join their networks.

4.5. Related projects and initiatives

There is also a fifth identified group which is the cooperation with other similar projects to facilitate synergies and sharing of project results and making use of project networks.

Related projects or initiatives are a crucial vector for the development of CYCLOPES. They are an important stakeholder category, as their environment needs to be aligned with CYCLOPES' approach, avoiding possible overlap and enhancing complementary synergies.

CYCLOPES continues to engage with a wide range of EU Projects and European and national activities, already identified during the preparation phase. In the following table there is an exemplification of the links already developed:

Table 5 List of EU projects and initiatives

EU PROJECTS

Project Acronym	CYCLOPES partner	Field of Activities
i-LEAD, i-LEAnet, i-ProcureNet	PPHS, HO, UCD CCI	Identification of LEA needs, cybercrime, standardisation, procurement, market & research watch
ARCSAR Project	LAUREA	Arctic security and emergency first response
EU-HYBNET Project NOTIONES Project CYBERSPACE Project	LAU, PPHS, ZITIS	Hybrid threats, future trends, cyber and future technologies, innovation mapping and recommendations for standardisation
ASGARD, TITANIUM, ANITA, TRILLION, FORMOBILE, UNITY, PROPHETS, ROXANNE, MAGNETO, COPKIT	TNO, HO, PPHS, ASI, MUP, GDCOC	Fight against crime and terrorism, establish new knowledge to explore the feasibility of a new or improved technology, product, process, service or solution
AIDA	CRI, CENTRIC	Artificial intelligence data analysis
RESPOND-A	IANUS	Next-generation equipment tools and mission-critical strategies for first responders
SPARTA, CONCORDIA, ECHO, SANCUS	PPHS, LAU, IANUS	Cybersecurity, information security technologies, knowledge and technology transfer, competence hub for innovation
TENSOR	CRI, CENTRIC	Terrorist activity recognition, data protection
FORESIGHT VISION	CRI, TNO, CENTRIC	Improve cybersecurity, roadmap for the development of AI in Europe
GRACE	CRI, CENTRIC	Bio-based industries joint technology initiative
CYBERSECPRO	LAU	Cybersecurity
INFINITY	CENTRIC	Cybercrime, terrorists and hybrid threats
TRESPASS	TNO	Training in secure and privacy-preserving biometrics, security protection
Stairs4Security	ASI	Innovation and research for security, standardisation in the CBRNe sectors
BDVe	TNO	Big data value ecosystem
DRIVER+	TNO	Innovation in crisis management for European resilience
SIIP	MUP	Audio and voice analysis, speaker identification for security applications
Lion DC	PPHS, GDCOC	Fight against online drug crimes
Anti-FinTer	IANUS	AI investigative technologies, online cross-border financing of terrorism
	CENTRIC, SPA	Fight against crime and terrorism, research and validate innovative lawful-interception measures
UNDERSERVED	CENTRIC, UCD	A platform for reporting and analysing cyberattacks /threats to humanitarian sector
ENACT	NP	Network for security R&I, fight against crime & terrorism
STARLIGHT	CRI, IANUS, TNO, BFP, SPA,	AI tools and capabilities improving investigatory practices, LEAs autonomy and

	CENTRIC, NP, ZITiS	resilience in the use of AI for tackling major criminal threats.
ALIGNER	SPA	Opportunities, challenges, needs, and risks emerging from the use of AI technologies in law enforcement.
TCO Cluster: ALLIES FRISCO TATE	PPHS	Support Hosting Service Providers (HSPs) in Europe in complying with the EU's new Terrorist Content Online (TCO) Regulation.
UNCOVER	SPA, ZITiS, NP	Digital investigation, development of an efficient steganalysis framework for uncovering hidden data in digital media
ARICA	PPHS	support law enforcement agencies in their fight against child sexual abuse. Development of technologies, enhancing investigation of CSAM.
CPORT	BFP	Platform to report online child sexual abuse material to authorities and national contact points
CC-DRIVER	PPHS	Researching cybercriminality to design new methods to prevent, investigate, and mitigate cybercriminal behaviour.
OVERCLOCK	ZITiS	Using Encryption Research for Criminal LOCKdown, digital investigation, cracking strong encryption on devices used in criminal activities.
eFirst	BFP, SPLV, PPHS, UCD, GUCI	E-learning platform on electronic evidence dedicated to LEAs, Tax authorities etc.
National Initiatives		
UK National Cyber Project	CENTRIC	Cybercrime, cybersecurity
Cryptocurrency investigation SG	CENTRIC – Europol	Cryptocurrency training game for law enforcement professionals
EU Strategy Documents		
Council of Europe Guidelines for LEA	CRI	Fighting against crime and terrorism (including cybercrime)

4.6. Stakeholders' needs

Stakeholders' needs are a crucial part in the project dissemination plan as we need to understand and plan for relevant information to be shared, and selected stakeholders to be targeted based on different kinds of events. Figure 3 below illustrates the stakeholders' input/output to and of the project based on their needs identified.

Figure 3 Stakeholders' input/output to and of the project based on their needs identified

4.6.1. Practitioners

Practitioners in the CYCLOPES project are a specific stakeholder that includes only LEAs. It is easy for us to distinguish the needs of this group from the rest as they are mainly interested in the identification of the gaps, needs and capabilities in the cybercrime/cybersecurity area. Practitioners need to have access to all project reliable information and integrate it in their daily work.

Practitioners are in the epicentre of the CYCLOPES project. They comprise the network and therefore, they should be included in all project activities.

4.6.2. Industry Including SMEs

The industry group can be divided into the following categories.

- Manufacturers need to be aware of current trends and threats related to cybercrime in order to be able to offer new innovative solutions that could help LEAs fighting cybercrime
- Service providers have to be aware of the potential threats and risks associated with cybercrime/cybersecurity and propose/implement appropriate security solutions to prevent the risks and to mitigate the impact of some crisis and vulnerabilities.
- Vendors need to be aware of the trends and needs of the practitioners to make available new technologies for procurement by LEAs
- Industry Associations need to be aware of the CYCLOPES aims and create appropriate industry associations for example dedicated to cybercrime/cybersecurity
- The suppliers need guidance into the security requirements and examples of security solutions proven to be effective in the targeted context to improve the security provided by their products and services.

- Industry Think Tanks need guidance into trends and security requirements for uptake and creating trends in the market.

Security Industry needs insight into trends and risks that occur in the cybercrime domain. It also requires opportunities to validate novel security solutions in such eco-systems.

4.6.3. Scientific Community

CYCLOPES can be relevant for the scientific community concerning cybercrime to provide feedback on the feasibility, applicability in real life scenario of project results. More specifically the idea would be to:

- Provide guidance in terms of the interpretation of requirements in scope,
- Exchange research results, to efficiently use available resources.

The results of such an action will be interesting for the scientific community also for other stakeholders that may access the relevant information.

4.6.4. Policymakers

Policymakers need to be aware of the project results in order to understand the requirements for innovation and further standardization and to be able to adequately include in the future policies new and innovative ways for LEAs to combat cybercrime while ensuring all are well within SEL frameworks. It is crucial for them to receive the correct information in order to act accordingly.

The integration of inputs coming from diverse stakeholders can also be used to support the implementation of related projects and initiatives.

4.6.5. Related projects and initiatives

Having cooperation with other projects and initiatives is crucial to ensure the CYCLOPES project's successful implementation and relevancy. Similarly, also the related projects must know what is happening in the CYCLOPES project via publications and other channels as described in the task 5.1 of the WP5.

A crucial part of this group is to synchronise work for example, if i-LEAD has one annual workshop dedicated to cybercrime; CYCLOPES must know which topics are planned for forthcoming workshops to avoid duplication of tasks. Same goes for the other initiatives and their relevant actions. CYCLOPES must ensure that proper engagement happens with this group in order to maximize impact and relevancy of work.

5. Key Messages

Throughout the project, dissemination and communication efforts are developed in such a way that they communicate the main messages the project intends to share between the identified target groups.

The messages are selected carefully according to the needs of the stakeholders and the project activity in question. Mainly the messages are created based on the following questions:

1. Whom are we targeting?
2. What is the need of the project activity and stakeholder (benefit)?
3. What needs to be disseminated (Message)?

Table 6 CYCLOPES objectives that can be used to direct messages to targeted audiences

	Practitioners	Industry Inc. SMEs	Policymakers	Scientific community	Related Projects and Initiatives
WP1 Project Management & Security Matters					
Objectives related to the Project Management and security matters					
Achieve Project objectives	To get access to the achievement of project Objectives	To get access to the opportunities to further improve project outputs	To gain a better understanding of the project for future influence on Policies	To get the opportunity to give feedback on project outputs	To get a better understanding of the project, enhance collaboration and avoid overlap
WP2 Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements					
Objectives related to practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements					
To identify Gaps, Needs & Capabilities	To be able to give feedback on the identification of Gaps, Needs and capabilities	To be able to suggest solutions to G, N & C	To have access to the G, N & S identified	To have access and give feedback to the G, N & C identified. Stimulate further research.	To be aware of the G, N & C identified and to facilitate synergies
To increase European Stakeholders' knowledge of the cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on Cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats
To test Innovation to enhance practitioners' measures against cybercrime	To be aware of the tests and give feedback on Innovation	To be aware of the test and to be able to take a position on the market and contribute to cybercrime needs	To be aware of the test as input for potential follow up action when needed	To be aware of the results of the tests and use them	To be aware of the test
To support the extension of actors in the European Network	To be part of the European Network combating cybercrime		To support the network of LEAs combating cybercrime	To participate to the events of the project	To participate to the events of the project

against cybercrime					
WP3 Research, innovation and market watch					
Objectives related to research, innovation and market watch					
To map the needs for innovations.	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping
To monitor and select available innovative solutions for measures against cybercrime threats	To contribute to the solution selection	To be aware of the selected solutions as input for potential follow up action when needed	To understand any policy-related points relevant to solutions selected	To contribute to the possible solutions	CYCLOPES to use potential project results to map innovations
To arrange joint exercises/events with detailed scenarios of cybercrime threats	To be aware of the events and attend them	To be aware of the events and attend them	To observe the events and gain understanding of the tech and how it impacts policy	To be aware of the events and attends them	To be aware of the events and attend them
WP4 Standardisation and innovation uptake					
Objectives of the standardisation and innovation uptake					
To identify priorities related to fighting cybercrime requiring standardisation	To support and be aware of the priorities requiring standardisation	To be aware of the standardisations and see its potential influence on the market via select public reports	To be aware of the standardisation requirements	To be aware of the standardisation requirement via select public reports	To be aware of the standardisation requirement via select public reports and uptake of results as input
To compile recommendations for standardisation activities	To support the compilation of most critical G,N & C requiring standardisation		To be aware of the recommendations as input for potential follow up action when needed	To be aware of the standardisation requirement via select public reports	To be aware of the standardisation requirement via select public reports and uptake of results as input

To deliver Policy Briefs, Position Papers and Recommendations	To be aware of the documents and to participate in workshops	To be aware of the documents produced and to participate in events	To be aware of the documents produced as input for potential follow up action when needed, to participate in workshops	To be aware of the publications	To be aware of the publications for potential results uptake
WP5 CYCLOPES community building					
Objectives of CYCLOPES community building					
to establish, build and maintain cooperation with other practitioners, practitioner networks and other relevant stakeholders	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.
Extend the network of practitioners with new members	To join the network				
WP6 Communication, dissemination and exploitation					
Objectives of Communication, dissemination and exploitation					
To disseminate results and interact with other related networks	To be aware of the main results and objectives of CYCLOPES	To be aware of the results in order to take a position on the market	To be aware of the main results of CYCLOPES To have the opportunity to improve actual policy	To be aware of the main results of CYCLOPES	To be aware of the main results of CYCLOPES
To create conditions for better interaction with LEAs, industry, academia, EC, EU agencies and member states. Support enriching existing network combating cybercrime	To be part of the CYCLOPES Network and have access to project resources aimed at the network members.	To be aware of the network existence and be able to find relevant information	To be aware of the network existence and be able to find relevant information	To be able to interact with the project in various channels.	To be able to interact with the project in various channels.

with practitioners.					
WP7 Societal, Ethical and Legal Connections Related to Cybercrime					
Objectives related to Societal, Ethical and Legal Connections Related to Cybercrime					
analyse the potential and actual societal, ethical and legal (SEL) challenges related to cybercrime investigation activities	to be aware of potential societal and ethical issues related to cybercrime G,N&C and solutions as input and output	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards new innovations	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards new innovations and potential uptake of results	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards new innovations in cybercrime	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards cybercrime innovations
To provide clear forms throughout the project that take into consideration SEL issues	To be aware of limitations/opportunities of joining the network	To be aware of limitations/opportunities of providing input/output in/of the project taking into account SEL challenges		To be aware of limitations/opportunities of providing input/output in/of the project taking into account SEL challenges	To be aware of limitations/opportunities of providing input/output in/of the project taking into account SEL challenges
WP8 Ethics requirements					
Objectives related to Ethics Requirements are for administrative purposes.					
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

6. Dissemination tools

6.1. Online dissemination channels

Online dissemination tools play a key role in the overall project dissemination. The advantage of having an online presence is that it facilitates a quick way to reach targeted audiences and raise interest among the cybercrime threat community and the civil society in general.

6.1.1. CYCLOPES Website

PPHS has created a dedicated CYCLOPES website (Figure 4), which serves as the primary channel to support communication and dissemination of project information and results. The website maintains the same graphical identity as the other communication tools used within the project.

The website is accessible from desktop as well as mobile devices on the following address <https://cyclopes-project.eu>. It hosts publicly available content produced by the project such as

relevant upcoming events, news, public deliverables, project information, network information and so on.

Figure 4 CYCLOPES website

6.1.1.1. Design and Architecture

The current structure (Figure 5) might receive slight changes throughout the project as the project matures and more information and/or needs are identified.

Home page

Represents the landing page of the website and an overview of the project and navigation system for ease of access to project information (Figure 4).

Figure 5 CYCLOPES website architecture

News

This section holds the latest blog news published by the project. It provides a way to quickly find the latest updates by the project. News will be published accordingly on need basis.

About

The about page is holds information regarding the project CYCLOPES and what it stands for, objectives, network information, consortium, various boards information, work plan and so on.

Events

The events page features all upcoming and past events organised by the project such as workshops, live exercises and where the project participates. Events are also featured in the news section.

Contact

The project website provides a contact form as well as contact information for general inquiries.

Get Involved

This section of the navigation system is dedicated to two subpages: For LEAs and For Research & Industry.

- For LEAs

The page displays information that concerns LEAs mainly an introduction to the project objectives and how LEA's can contribute to the project. There is also a call to action to join the CYCLOPES network.

- For Research & Industry

On this page, information aimed particularly at research and industry is provided in order to inform them about the project relevant information as well as ways they can contribute.

Downloads

This page offers a way to list downloadable content that is produced by the project. This can be i.e. public deliverables, newsletters, press releases, event reports and so on.

Partners

This page is dedicated to presenting the partners of CYCLOPES projects, including consortium partners, community members, applicable groups, connected projects and individual stakeholders.

Join Us

This page offers a form that interested parties can use to express their intent to join the CYCLOPES network.

Newsletter subscription

In addition to the current page sections, the CYCLOPES website also offers a way for the visitors to sign-up for the newsletter. The form can be located by scrolling down (footer area) and can be accessed throughout the website. This section is still in development at the time of writing the deliverable hence more updates will come later.

6.1.1.2. Security and Maintenance

For security reasons not a lot of detailed information can be disclosed with regards to technology, servers and security measures taken.

The C&D team will regularly review the website traffic and user behaviour to monitor security threats, and will keep the systems patched and upgraded, when possible, to ensure adequate protection is provided.

6.1.1.3. GDPR Compliance

A link to the privacy policy is provided as a pop-up banner to the users to read before accessing the website. This informs the user of the data we gather, any tracking performed and the cookie policy. The user will have the choice to continue using the site under the set conditions or navigate away.

An agreement policy informs the visitors on the reasons the website collects any information and how this information will be used, as in the case with newsletter subscriptions, contact forms and registration to platforms.

Visitors have the right to request to know the data the website holds about them and for its destruction upon request. However, some data of offensive nature i.e. deliberate hacking attempts may be held for security and forensic purposes.

6.1.2. CYCLOPES Private Areas

The main objective of the CYCLOPES private area is to facilitate communication and exchange of knowledge with the members of the advisory boards, project partners and network members. The CYCLOPES workspace is created in the Microsoft TEAMS collaborative tool which is provided by the project coordinator PPHS.

This CYCLOPES workspace enables its members to:

- Share and stock documents
- Organise meetings
- Manage directories and contacts
- Discuss special issues
- Other general collaboration needs

To create solid working relations and to achieve the desired results of the CYCLOPES project, it is imperative that all partners work together and communicate freely. Internal communications are essential to establish a strong grasp of the project's vision, values and objectives. All members of the consortium should feel included and integrated with the efforts, in all of the work packages. All-inclusive communication among all project partners and participants is critical for the PMO to follow and monitor the project progress. Moreover, it will boost team building and encourage individual accountability for the achieved results. The foundation for good communication is consistency. Therefore, a regular cadence for group meetings will be set. The following list forms the foundation for promoting good internal communications:

- Regular consortium meetings; at least once a year (General Assembly)
- Monthly online meetings
- WP team meetings through telephone or video conferences
- Quarterly coordination meetings (Project Board) through online meetings,
- Access to the on-line communication platform dedicated to the CYCLOPES project (Microsoft Teams);

- Regular contact between the Project Management Office, the WP Leaders and other contributors;
- Reports every EU reporting period.

6.1.3. Social media

As we have seen through experience, social media platforms offer a great opportunity to target desired audiences to keep them updated with project progress. Their simplicity in publishing content and their openness offers an easy way to reach audiences regardless of the device. The WP6 leader and the project coordinator have decided that for our specific project needs, LinkedIn and X accounts would be more favourable as opposed to Facebook, Instagram and other platforms.

6.1.3.1. X

An X account has been created for the CYCLOPES project called project-cyclopes. (Figure 6). The initial plan was to name the account cyclopes-project, the same as the website, however this at the time was unavailable. Another limiting factor was that the account name had to be comprised of no more than 15 characters. During a WP meeting held on September 2021, we decided to keep the current account names and not pursue the change as mentioned in the D6.11.

To support project activities, we will continue to use the (@) mentions as well as (#) hashtags where appropriate, for our posts to be easily found by interested parties.

The current hashtags planned for use in CYCLOPES project communications. **On domain specific dissemination, it is recommended that at least the first two are used in combination with other relevant hashtags. I.e. #cybercrime #lawenforcement #digitalforensics and so on.** Similarly, when targeting a specific organisation, it is recommended to mention them either via hashtag (#) or tag (@).

- #cyclopesnetwork
- #cybercrime
- #LEA

We are planning on posting on X more frequently and therefore are expecting the number of followers to increase as well.

Figure 6 CYCLOPES X profile

6.1.3.2. LinkedIn

A LinkedIn account has also been created and named **project-cyclopes**. (Figure 7) (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-cyclopes/>). With the same vision in mind as the X one, LinkedIn has been recognised as the best platform aimed at reaching professionals which allows posting longer content than X. With that in mind we are using LinkedIn to promote network expansion and keep our followers updated with project news and materials. Since the account's creation, the number of followers has been steadily increasing and LinkedIn remains an important channel for communication and dissemination. We post on the channel frequently, and therefore expect the number of followers to continue growing throughout the project lifecycle.

Figure 7 CYCLOPES LinkedIn page

6.1.4. YouTube

CYCLOPES has a YouTube account for hosting and sharing video and audio materials for professionals and general public. This will be utilised in the dissemination of project results. This is open for all project partners to use in relation to CYCLOPES communications. YouTube is mostly known for hosting video material, but it is also frequently used as a platform for podcasts. We believe that YouTube would be an effective channel of communication towards both wider audience and professionals interested in cybersecurity.

6.1.5. Newsletter

Newsletters include project updates and a call for contributions on project activities. It describes achievements and upcoming activities, and it is shared amongst the partners and the CYCLOPES network. The newsletter is also published on the project website, sent out to interested recipients, and made available on social media. Newsletter is produced at least biannually, and more frequently depending on the activities to be shared. We are also taking measures to spread awareness of the newsletter to audiences who haven't already subscribed to it via social media. See Annex VI

6.1.6. Webinars

The webinars are an additional opportunity to disseminate the project findings and increase the overall impact. CYCLOPES partners have been organising webinars in the year 2024 as well as planning to host another one in the beginning of 2025 on a range of topics. The webinars' topics can be complementary leading to a major event or stand-alone discussions on a pressing topic.

6.1.7. Materials for new network members

It is important that new members feel welcome to the CYCLOPES network. Therefore, introductory materials have been prepared and are shared to them after joining the network. These materials are prepared by WP5 with the support of WP6. These include project leaflet, network poster and other relevant materials. (See Annexes III, V, IX).

6.1.8. Publications, press releases, articles

Consortium members, partners and external entities will collaborate on joint publications. Press releases and articles will describe project progress and outcomes. As well, project experts will publish in reputable journals and deliver papers at relevant conferences to enhance project impact. Also, at least five position papers on the main results of the project will be published. White Papers will be written for policy purposes.

Planned policy briefs, topics, responsible partner and delivery time:

- Policy paper I. on digital forensics foresight (ZITIS - M12),
- Policy paper II. on ethical framework for cybercrime investing (CRI - M24),
- Policy paper III. on practitioners needs and requirements (CENTRIC – M36),
- Policy paper IV. on areas require more standardization (ASI – M48),
- Policy paper V. on practitioners needs and requirements – roadmap (PPHS – M54)

The articles and press media will be targeted at the target audience but also to other media channels (Table 7) that could maximize the reach. The following table shows a few examples of such news outlets, however the list is expected to grow in the process.:

Table 7 Few press agencies that can be used to maximise audience reach

Media	Country	Type
Reuters	Europe	Press Agency
Bloomberg	Europe	Press Agency
Agence France Presse	France	Press Agency
Athens News Agency	Greece	Press Agency

There is also a good opportunity to target the following European Commission channels:

- **Horizon Magazine** <http://horizonmagazine.eu/>
- **CORDIS website** <https://cordis.europa.eu/es>
- **DGHome Protection of public spaces newsletter**
https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/index.cfm?service_id=1410
- **Conferences and events** organised by the European Commission

6.1.9. Public deliverables

Due to the sensitivity of the subject, deliverables of the CYCLOPES project are mostly restricted for public view. However, some deliverables after a process of scrutiny and after they are accepted by the EC, are published for the public and they are to be found on the EU platforms, such as CORDIS and many more, website downloads area, newsletter and so on. These documents are crucial and contain detailed descriptions of the results.

6.2. Dissemination tracking form

An online dissemination tracking form is dedicated to gather information from partners on their dissemination activities. This has been identified as a more user-friendly alternative compared to the Excel file that has been used previously. In order to prevent spam

submissions due to the public nature of this document, the link address is redacted and can be found by contacting the WP6 lead partner.

6.3. Dissemination guidelines booklet

1 – 2 pages booklet on dissemination guidelines will be created to support the dissemination work of the partners. This will increase the dissemination efforts and encourage partners to share project results in social media and other outlets.

6.4. Collaborative events to further maximise impact

6.4.1. Practitioner workshops

Practitioner workshops are the very engine of the project, organised as physical workshops, if the COVID situation allows, where practitioners' (i.e. LEAs) capabilities, gaps and requirements are identified, and common priorities towards innovations and standardisation are defined:

- Digital Forensics,
- Cybercrime as Affecting People,
- and Cybercrime as Affecting Systems.

A total of 15 workshops will be organized throughout the project lifespan, 3 each year. This task is highly relevant for practitioners (LEAs).

6.4.2. Annual Joint Live Exercises

The practitioner workshops provide data for the project's market and research watch, and the selected products and solutions identified by the market and research scans have been tested within annual Joint Live Exercises since the start of the project and will continue to do so until the end

In addition to practitioners, relevant representatives of industry and academia are among the key stakeholders to be invited to these exercises.

There are **5 total planned** joint live exercises and the purpose is to:

- Test the identified technology against a baseline of a representative scenario.
- Expose practitioners to new software and enable them to make a hands-on assessment outside of typical demos.
- Enable developers of technologies to receive direct feedback on how their solution addresses the gaps identified by practitioners and help them move to higher TRL solutions.

The task is highly relevant to the industry and SMEs.

6.4.3. Annual dissemination events

Dissemination events have been successfully sharing project results to a large spectrum of stakeholders and have ensured efficient engagement of stakeholders such as the industry and academia. These events foster network activities, raise awareness of the project and bring together relevant practitioners who may wish to join the CYCLOPES network and its activities. A series of Dissemination events taking place yearly have been planned at the beginning of the project:

- First dissemination event organized by PPHS in Poland or Brussels (M12);
- Second dissemination event organized by PPHS online (M29)
- Third dissemination event organized by PPHS & ASI in Vienna (M36);

- Fourth dissemination event organized by SPA in Sweden (M48);
- Fifth dissemination event organized by MUP in Croatia (M58)

The events provide a platform to discuss the project's findings and specifically the recommendations for innovation uptake (incl. industrialisation) and standardisation.

6.4.4. Annual standardisation workshops

Based on information gathered within task 4.2, CYCLOPES selects at least one topic to be further elaborated during a dedicated yearly workshop. Workshops are organised independently, or in cooperation with particular technical committees' workshops or conferences. The ambition is to promote standardisation as an effective tool in the fight against cybercrime, while exploring the opportunities to streamline processes and procedures that will maintain efficacy and maximise effectiveness throughout the project duration.

These events can be organized at the same time with the dissemination events due to shared scope and outreach objectives.

6.4.5. External Events, Cooperation and Information Exchange:

Participation to external events organised by relevant networks and organisations including cooperation and exchange of knowledge is one of the key elements of project results dissemination. CYCLOPES partners have regularly participated to **external events** (relevant conferences, seminars, workshops, fairs and other gatherings of experts, industry and academia), as often as 15 times yearly. These events present unique opportunities for project dissemination to stakeholders, and to obtain feedback that allows CYCLOPES to maintain progress with the latest trends and conditions.

Outreach and clustering activities that aim to engage other interested consortia and RDI projects looking to strengthen resilience to cybercrime represent an important element of the project's dissemination plan. New perspectives and visions for project success will continue to emerge through active collaboration with other European consortia . Special attention is set on alignment with EC's Community of Users events, so that the wider user community can exploit the outcomes of CYCLOPES.

The project consortium are encouraged to actively track and participate to relevant external events. This supports the outreach, overall visibility and the dissemination of results..

Figure 8 CYCLOPES partners represent CYCLOPES to various external events during the year 2024

7. Communication Strategy

7.1. Visual materials

The visual identity is well defined by the project's logo (created at the time of the submission) and by the document templates (deliverables and Word document template provided at M1 by PPHS). A PowerPoint template has been updated in M21 to better reflect CYCLOPES existing branded materials, notebook, website, leaflets, etc. These are provided as annexes at the end of document.

A promotional package was also created at M4 and includes:

- CYCLOPES Roll-up banners to be used during project events and events CYCLOPES partners will attend. These are also provided as digital and hard copies.
- CYCLOPES Leaflet to be disseminated during events in general, both in soft and hard copies.
- CYCLOPES – themed stationary supplies such as pens and notebooks distributed to participants of various project events.

Additionally, a general project presentation has been created using the updated presentation template showcasing the project activities, network coverage and other relevant information. The presentation has been regularly updated and maintained in cooperation with WP1, WP5 and WP6. The last update took place on October 2024 and can be found in the project document repository.

All communication materials, such as the leaflets, roll-up, and any upcoming materials will be updated also according to the needs of the consortium, and dated information as the project progresses.

7.1.1. Leaflet

The CYCLOPES Leaflets are designed in a similar fashion as the roll-up and the website. Leaflet is an A4 document that includes a brief description of the project, its objectives, funding, as well as a call to action that is added in order to invite potential network members to join the network and other stakeholders to provide their contributions (Annex III).

Two versions are offered: a smaller digital version and for print.

The current leaflet differs greatly from the content to its design compared to the one provided in the D6.11 Project branding. This was a necessary redesign in order to meet the project quality demands for a more informative and visually attractive set of marketing materials.

The leaflet has been regularly updated to reflect current project activities beyond what is required by DOA.

In addition to support WP5, a network related leaflet was also produced and disseminated throughout various project channels and is available for download publicly on the website.

7.1.2. Roll-up

The CYCLOPES Roll-up is one of the main materials designed to draw the attention of potential audiences especially when the audience can physically or digitally see them. Roll-ups serve as a first touch point with the project and paint the first impressions. Experience has taught us that they are the most effective when used while representing the project to varied audiences that are in crowd or passers-by, but also in keynote speeches, vlogs or video conferences.

As such, the Roll-up is designed to be minimalistic, representing the theme of the project via the chosen colour palette in line with the website and the logo. Furthermore, it includes contact details to invite further collaboration opportunities and contact information including social media (Annex II). Two versions are developed: the online version and the print. They differ slightly from one another. This was necessary due to its size for the writings to be readable on screen.

The current Roll-up differs greatly from the content to its design compared to the one provided in the D6.11 Project branding. This was a necessary redesign in order to meet the project quality demands for a more informative and visually attractive set of marketing materials.

7.1.3. Poster

A CYCLOPES network poster (ANNEX V) has been created in collaboration with WP5 to be used in the EAFS22 conference as well as other events in the future. The poster contains similar information as the network leaflet except in a more graphical representation.

7.1.4. Flyers and banners

For each CYCLOPES organised event such as joint live exercise, workshop or webinar, there is a flyer designed and published in all dissemination channels. Also, banners are being created for social media. In the banner, a QR code that directs visitors to the network registration link in the project website, can be displayed. Examples of flyers and banners can be seen as ANNEX IV.

7.1.5. Video and audio materials

Laurea produces video materials to support the project's communication, especially for event and network promotions. Laurea has explored the possibility to produce podcasts to share the activities and lessons learned from the project to the wider audience.

In conclusion, Laurea possesses technical capabilities and assistance for producing podcasts. Due to limited resources this might be challenging to execute. In case of potentially significant ROI, the idea can be taken for further discussion with the project coordinator.

7.2. Communication policy

The CYCLOPES project partners must be involved as much as possible in making dissemination materials especially presentations, flyers, blogs, newsletters, and press releases. Their contribution will be requested particularly in areas where they will have more opportunity for capacity building. All CYCLOPES beneficiaries will be potential contributors for WP6 dissemination.

Beyond the overall understanding, we may use the following internal protocols when planning to communicate externally in a form of online media tools.

7.2.1. Social media

All partners will continue to update the WP6 Lead partner with quick updates of upcoming or past events and/or news related to the work they have completed/will be completed. WP6 lead partner will update the social media channels based on the information shared by the partners.

The lead partner will continue to publish and maintain the social media tools based on their knowledge and experience.

All partners should continue to contribute to social media communication through their own organisational pages/feeds using relevant hashtags.

A calendar type solution has been created to ease the predictability and organising of social media posts. The goal is to make a new post in both LinkedIn and X every 2-3 days. In the future, we also aim to post about upcoming events 2-3 times between the publication of the event and the event itself. This is to ensure awareness of and participation in the events. We plan to use our channels more frequently for calls to action to join the network and to communicate about other activities of the CYCLOPES' network.

7.2.2. News, articles and press releases

Dissemination leader first modifies and checks the proposed dissemination material (e.g. press release) submitted in good time by the partner/beneficiary to allow for sufficient review and forwards the material to the coordinator.

The coordinator will provide final validation of the material to be communicated externally through selected channels (e.g. website).

7.2.3. EU-Acknowledgement

All project dissemination and documentation materials should use the EU-funding acknowledgement in accordance with the grant agreement and latest [EU guidelines](#). This includes the sentence below and the EU-flag logo (Figure 9).

“Funded by the European Union”

Figure 9 EU acknowledgement flag and text

All sorts of external communication are encouraged to promote the CYCLOPES project and its results. The dissemination strategy of CYCLOPES is streamlined through this Dissemination Plan.

Provisions are made to provide coordination, consistency, and quality of publications for the benefit of the project's reputation. A second purpose is to give visibility within the project to any public relation activities of the partners.

Any evidence of a dissemination activity must be stored on the project repository (i.e. "Full Paper" version and presentation material).

In general, the dissemination activities, including but not restricted to publications and presentations shall be governed by Article 29 of the Grant Agreement. Specifically, partners will be responsible for including the EU emblem, acknowledgement of EU funding, and disclaimers.

7.2.4. Point of Contact for Dissemination and Communication

Each consortium partner assigns a dissemination and communication Point of Contact (POC), or preferably two persons, who are responsible for dissemination and communication activities, as well as for social media liaison and requests.

The D&C PoC will ensure that the CYCLOPES Dissemination and Communication Plan is properly implemented and that the guidelines for dissemination and communication are respected and followed. In addition, the D&C PoC will monitor D&C activities.

7.2.5. Publication procedures

Given that the project is dealing with potential sensitive information there are a set of guidelines to follow in order to coordinate the participation of partners in dissemination activities and conferences (both in European and at international level) and properly notify the Commission of any event:

- It is essential that adequate time for considering the publication or participation in an event is given. Therefore, the notification may be circulated as soon as possible and no less than **30 days in advance** for publication of an event, **14 days in advance** for an event requiring online participation and at least **30 days in advance** for an event requiring physical participation. The notification may be submitted to the coordinator and/or Dissemination Manager.
- The application may include, if possible, a copy of the conference program together with a rationale describing the conference and explaining the proposed role of CYCLOPES – i.e. networking, presentation of results, poster session, etc.
- Any partner in the consortium can publish its own results, it only needs to notify the dissemination manager and coordinator and fulfil the EC requirements hereafter identified. It is however preferred that common publications arise as result of cooperation among the partners.

- Unless the Commission requests otherwise, any notice or publication by the contractors about the project, including at a conference or seminar, must specify that the project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme and may display the European Commission logo provided in Figure 9. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. A pre-print or an abstract of the paper, if digital format online, a link should be sent to the coordinator and dissemination manager.
- Any notice or publication by the partners, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify a disclaimer that it reflects only the author's view and that the project partners nor the European Commission are not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.
- If a result is shared by several partners, the publication needs the approval of all the partners involved. The notification submitted to the project coordinator will have to be circulated to all the partners involved. If there is no response, approval is granted.
- Participants may provide to the Coordinator and Dissemination Manager, a copy of the concise written report produced for the project within reasonable time unless a force majeure beyond the scope of the authors prevents this from happening.
- The attendee may provide, where possible, a copy of the conference proceedings or a suitable extract to the Coordinator.
- The provisions of the Contract and the Consortium Agreement should be taken into account in dissemination of results of the project.
- The cost and frequency of the conference attendance should always be minimised and kept in proportion to the size and resources of the Project.

7.2.6. Partners' own press releases and other media contacts

All partners can send out press releases on their own. Partners willing to issue their own press releases must contact the Dissemination Manager to make sure the effort is properly disseminated in the CYCLOPES channels.

For all other public project related communication, the use of the CYCLOPES logo and acknowledgement that the work was derived from the support of the project or the EC funding. When it comes to IPR, all publications must follow the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

7.2.7. Image rights

Notes on image quality and image rights needs to be paid attention at all publication activities. The general recommendation for the image quality is shown in the following Table 8. In the case of picture rights, the origin of the picture as well as the creator must be mentioned. During the project, the author is always responsible for obtaining appropriate image rights, whether for printing publications or web-based publications. The general recommendations are:

Table 8 Guidelines on the use of images in publications

Quality	<i>Images for publications in print, 300 dpi (Size 100 x 150mm) Images for web, 160 dpi (Size 60 x 60mm). Images should always be optimized for web. I.e. minify them from original sizes. If this is not done they will negatively impact the website load speed and SEO.</i>
Rights	© Institution/Company or author, origin

7.3. Crisis communication process and actions

The term Crisis is defined by the Cambridge Dictionary as “a time of great disagreement, confusion, or suffering” as well as “an extremely difficult or dangerous point in a situation”.

As every other organisation of people, a project can face a huge number of confusing issues such as bad publicity, fake news and so on, which might ask from its partners the correct way of communicating and disseminating the appropriate messages. To avoid any disagreements, it is seen as necessary to appoint a Crisis Manager (CM) for CYCLOPES. A general protocol below in time of crisis should be followed:

- Step 1: A crisis has been detected by a partner and communicated to the CM
- Step 2: CM and the coordinator assess together if the situation can be considered as a Crisis Situation
- Step 3: If this is not the case, the process will be stopped here.
- If this is the case, CM will have 1 week to work on the appropriate Crisis Plan to propose to the coordinator which will have 2 days to accept or not the Plan.
- Step 4: If the Crisis Plan is not accepted, the coordinator oversees making clear amendments to be transmitted to CM within 2 days. CM has 2 days to reply to them. The process cannot be longer than 10 days.
- If the Crisis Plan is accepted, it is immediately applied within CYCLOPES.

The above process naturally excludes a potential data breach where slightly more urgent corrective measures are required to be taken, normally within 48 hours.

Possible corrective measures include but are not limited to the following:

- Disallow further communication with the affected system by the public.
- Change all passwords and other relevant private data in case there are users involved.
- Investigate logs and audit the severity and potential data loss.
- Inform all participants of the data breach and further details within 72 hours.
- Apply corrective measures and patch vulnerabilities.
- Prepare a public announcement.

8. Monitoring and assessment of dissemination and communication

Dissemination is measured using key performance indicators (KPIs) created based on the project objectives. The KPIs have been analysed and updated in each update of the DCP, in o. The following table (Table 9) shows the targets set forth for the successful implementation of D&C and reaching the intended impact of the project.

Project objectives:

OB1: To form a law enforcement agencies' network across Europe, combating cybercrime

OB2: To define the capability gaps and requirements of practitioners fighting cybercrime

OB3: To monitor development of new technologies, research activities and innovations applied to combatting cybercrime

OB4: To indicate priorities regarding domains requiring standardisation and innovation uptake

OB5: To cooperate with other networks of practitioners and relevant stakeholders fighting cybercrime

OB6: Increase the visibility of the CYCLOPES network to enlarge its stakeholder community and maximise its impact

OB7: To analyse societal, ethical and legal challenges related to cybercrime

Table 9 CYCLOPES Dissemination and Communication KPIs

Target					
KPIs		Level of performance			Partners involved
D&C Tools	Definition of indicator	Poor	Good	Excellent	
Project Website	The number of visits	Less than 100 per month	100-200 per month	more than 200 per month	Responsible: LAU, PPHS. Contributing to content: All
	The number of page views	Less than 200 per month	200-400 per month	more than 400 per month	
	Average time spent on website	Less than 15 sec.	15 sec. – 1 min.	more than 1 min.	
Social Media	Followers on LinkedIn	Less than 50 per year	80 on yearly basis	More than 80 on yearly basis	Responsible: LAU, PPHS. Contributing partners: All
	Followers on X	Less than 50 per year	50 on yearly basis	more than 50 on yearly basis	
	Number of posts	Less than 3 per month	3-5 per month	More than 5 per month	
Annual Joint Live Exercises	Number of practitioners per event	Less than 10 per event	10-15 per event	More than 15 per event	Responsible: SPA, (LAU, PPHS for D&C)

	Number of participants from the scientific community per event	Less than 3 per event	3-5 per event	More than 5 per event	Partners: PPHS, TNO, CENTRIC, ZITIS, UCD, CCI, all LEAs
	Number of participants from the Industry/SME per event	Less than 3 per event	3-5 per event	More than 5 per event	
Annual Dissemination Event	Number of participants per event	less than 30 per event	30 - 50 per event	more than 50 per event	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible: 1 st : PPHS 2 nd : PPHS 3 rd : UK Home 4 th : SPA 5 th : MUP Contributing: All partners
Annual Standardisation Workshop	Number of participants per event	less than 10 per event	10-30 per event	more than 30 per event	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible: ASI, Contributing: PPHS, ZITIS, all LEAs
Practitioner Workshops	Number of participants per workshop	Less than 10 (online) Less than 7 (physical)	10-15 (Online) 7-12 (physical)	More than 15 (online) More than 12 (physical)	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible: HO, (LAU, PPHS) Contributing: ZITIS, All LEAs except CPEB
Participation to External Events	Number of external events in which CYCLOPES participates	less than 3 per year	3-5 per year	more than 5 per year	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible partners: PPHS, Contributing partners: ALL
Liaison Activities and Synergies	Number of relevant projects/initiatives identified and contacted/invited at project events	Less than 4 on yearly basis	4-6 on yearly basis	more than 6 on yearly basis	Responsible: All D&C: LAU, PPHS
	Number of relevant organisations/communities/experts identified and contacted/invited at project events	less than 5 on yearly basis	5-10 on a yearly basis	More than 10 on a yearly basis	

	Number of cooperation activities (common events and other clustering activities)	less than 1 on a yearly basis	2-3 on a yearly basis	more than 3 on a yearly basis	
Link to the Community of Users	Number of 'CYCLOPES' presentations made during plenary meetings and thematic workshops	2 per year	2 -3 per year	more than 3 per year	Responsible: PPHS Contributing: ALL
Webinars	participants to the webinars	15-20 per webinar	20-30 per webinar	more than 30 per webinar	Responsible: PPHS Contributing: PPHS, IANUS, ZITIS, LAU, SPA, CPEB
Newsletters	Newsletters published	Less than 2 per year	2 per year	more than 2 per year	Responsible: LAU Participating partners: All
	Subscribers	20-50	50-100	more than 100	
CYCLOPES Community of Users	Number of new members (organisations not individuals)	0-5 per year	5-10 per year	more than 10 per year	All

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ANNEX I Glossary of Terms

Term	Definition/description
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EP	Exploitation Plan
PM	Project Manager
WP	Work Package
PC	Project Coordinator
QM	Quality Manager
CM	Crisis Manager
EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
EU	European Union
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency

ANNEX II Roll-up

CYCLOPES

**CYBERCRIME
LAW ENFORCEMENT
PRACTITIONERS' NETWORK**
An innovation-driven network of LEAs
combating cybercrime

**YOUR HELP IS NEEDED, PLEASE
GET IN TOUCH!**

**WE INVITE CONTRIBUTIONS FROM
LEAs , SMEs (industry) & RESEARCH (academia)**

FOLLOW OUR SOCIAL MEDIA

 @projectcyclopes

 project-cyclopes

CONTACT

 contact@cyclopes-project.eu

www.cyclopes-project.eu

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669.

CYCLOPES

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Annex IV CYCLOPES Flyers and banners

Annex V CYCLOPES Posters

JOIN THE CYBERCRIME LAW ENFORCEMENT PRACTITIONERS' NETWORK

JOIN THE NETWORK

COMMUNITY MEMBERS' BENEFITS

- 1. ACCESS TO EXPERTISE FROM MEMBERS ACROSS THE GLOBE, DRIVEN BY THE GROWING CYBERCRIME RISK
- 2. RECOGNIZED RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE TOPICS PRACTITIONERS CARE ABOUT
- 3. COMMON TERMINOLOGY, CONCEPTS - APPLICABLE PRACTICES (ACROSS COUNTRIES)
- 4. ANNUAL JOINT JOINT EXERCISES OR CONFERENCES THAT USE TOPICS OF INTEREST TO PRACTITIONERS FROM DIFFERENT COUNTRIES
- 5. ANNUAL CYCLOPES SUMMIT AND WEBINAR

CYCLOPES COMMUNITY MEMBERS GAIN THE FOLLOWING BENEFITS

- 1. ACCESS TO EXPERTISE FROM MEMBERS ACROSS THE GLOBE, DRIVEN BY THE GROWING CYBERCRIME RISK
- 2. RECOGNIZED RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE TOPICS PRACTITIONERS CARE ABOUT
- 3. COMMON TERMINOLOGY, CONCEPTS - APPLICABLE PRACTICES (ACROSS COUNTRIES)
- 4. ANNUAL JOINT JOINT EXERCISES OR CONFERENCES THAT USE TOPICS OF INTEREST TO PRACTITIONERS FROM DIFFERENT COUNTRIES
- 5. ANNUAL CYCLOPES SUMMIT AND WEBINAR

WHO CAN JOIN THE CYCLOPES COMMUNITY?

- EU LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES
- MEMBERS OF PARLIAMENTS
- ACADEMIC RESEARCHERS
- INDUSTRIAL FIRMS
- OPERATIONAL PUBLIC BODIES
- LEGAL PROFESSIONALS
- TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS
- RESEARCHERS

STANDARDS AGAINST CYBERCRIME

THE BENEFITS OF USING STANDARDS IN CYBERCRIME RELATED INVESTIGATIONS

STANDARDS ARE

- DESIGNED BY SUBJECT MATTER EXPERTS
- VERIFIED RECOMMENDATIONS
- RECOGNIZED PRACTICES

STANDARDS ENSURE

- COMMON TERMINOLOGY AND UNDERSTANDING
- ACCURACY, TRUSTWORTHINESS AND COMPLIANCE
- REPRODUCIBLE RESULTS
- ROBUSTNESS OF PROCESSES
- HARMONISED METHODS
- INTEROPERABILITY

WANT TO KNOW MORE ABOUT STANDARDS AND HOW TO USE THEM? SCAN THE QR CODE / VISIT THE PAGE

Funded by the European Union

CONTACT: info@cybercrime.eu

<https://www.cyclopes.eu>

CYCLOPES NETWORK GEOGRAPHICAL REGIONS

Europe

- Albania
- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Norway
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Serbia
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- United Kingdom

Oceania

- Australia

Africa

- Nigeria
- South Africa

Central America

- Panama

Annex VI CYCLOPES Newsletter

CYCLOPES Newsletter
July 2024

JOINT LIVE EXERCISES

14-16 May 2024, Wiesbaden, Germany

The third edition of the annual CYCLOPES Joint Live Exercises took place in Wiesbaden, Germany, at the BKA Bundeskriminalamt, on 14-16 May.

Officers across Europe had an opportunity to interact with several solutions in the Automotive Digital Forensic (ADF) domain. The covered topics included the challenges of vehicle forensics:

1. Data extraction and analysis from vehicle user data
2. Data extraction and analysis of diagnostic and ECUS
3. Data analysis of different types of vehicle data

The publicly available report is currently being prepared and will be made available soon.

CYCLOPES has an experienced Automotive Digital Forensic Group consisting of experts from Belgium, Cyprus, Germany, Sweden, Netherlands, Switzerland and UK. All Members are working within this domain and have a diverse skill set to help address challenges within ADF.

Many insights on how to investigate cybercrime affecting systems and networks were shared. Of particular focus were the role of online devices in perpetrating cybercrime and the challenges of securing evidence.

Funded by the European Union

INNOVATIONS AND COLLABORATIONS HIGHLIGHT THE CYCLOPES DISSEMINATION & CYBERCRIME COMMUNITY EVENT IN VIENNA 16-17 APRIL

Over the span of two action-packed days, Vienna became the focal point for global cybersecurity professionals and law enforcement agencies as it hosted the CYCLOPES Dissemination & Cybercrime Community Event. This major conference, held on April 16-17, 2024 at Austrian Standards International premises showcased the latest advancements and collaborative efforts in the fight against cybercrime.

The event included a mixture of tool demonstrations, keynote speeches, presentations and interactive sessions to address the priorities previously obtained through CYCLOPES practitioners' workshops. The event focused on diverse topics, such as access to data and lawful interception including network communications and cloud services, digital forensics, crypto assets as facilitators of cybercrime, cyber-related child sexual abuse and exploitation, AI technologies, and standardisation.

[Read full article on CYCLOPES website](#)

INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION AGAINST CYBERCRIME – EXPERIENCES FROM CYCLOPES & OCTOPUS 2023

Cybercrime is a global problem that requires international cooperation. Eskari Lappalainen's article describes how the CYCLOPES project has sought to cultivate international networks to build capacity in the fight against cybercrime. The critical importance of collaboration was also one of the key themes of the Octopus 2023 conference, in which members of Laurea's CYCLOPES team participated. The article explores how the themes of the CYCLOPES project and Octopus 2023 are related, how the Laurea team contributed to them, and what Laurea learned in return.

[Read full article on Laurea Journal](#)

SUMMARY

The rapid and sometimes disruptive developments in information technology complicate the work of international security and special authorities as it gets increasingly difficult to keep up with the changes and innovations in IT in the security sector. It is not just a capability gap that has emerged in the security agencies.

A further complication is that a strategic gap has arisen due to the high dynamics and complexity in IT. Unless there is a response to this issue, that gap will continue to grow.

The project CYCLOPES was initiated to reduce this gap. One of the project's main tasks is to conduct several workshops in the field of "Digital Forensics". The first workshop with the focus on "Mobile Devices and Wireless Technologies" took place in December 2021. This event was used to present in detail many impressions and experiences as well as the current status of European law enforcement agencies. Furthermore, the problems and needs of the participants were recorded in order to carry out a later analysis. The following areas were identified in the workshop for being vulnerable to or affected by capability gaps:

- Missing functionalities of the currently used software products
- Progressive development
- Cooperation with Internet Service Providers, Device Manufacturers and Software Providers
- Country specific differences

The resulting requirements are examined in more detail on the following pages.

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DRAWN CONCLUSIONS

MISSING FUNCTIONALITIES OF THE CURRENTLY USED SOFTWARE PRODUCTS

Many commercial products do not offer all the required functionalities. In the areas of encryption, data extraction and analysis the EU law enforcement agencies' needs exceed the current functionalities.

PROGRESSIVE DEVELOPMENT

The constant further development and fast improvement of smartphones both in terms of hardware and software always pose new challenges for law enforcement agencies. Changes due to fast update cycles, differing hardware and software parts even in one device model and the increasing number of device models creates a volatile area with a need for constant adaptation of available solutions and competences.

COOPERATION WITH INTERNET SERVICE PROVIDERS, DEVICE MANUFACTURERS AND SOFTWARE PROVIDERS

The law enforcement agencies have the big problem that not every international company cooperates during criminal investigations in one country or only up to a minimum. For many criminal investigations, the only way to get some specific information about the communication devices is to get support from the provider or the manufacturer. The problem is that not every company is willing to help.

COUNTRY SPECIFIC DIFFERENCES

Each country has different rules and laws that regulate criminal sanctions, it is difficult to provide a common European guideline or instructions on a detailed level. Even individual agencies in the same country often differ in the amount and quality of available equipment or training and number of staff.

[5/9]

ANNEX VII CYCLOPES Logo

ANNEX VIII Colour Codes

HEX	/	RGB
#edcd4f		237, 205, 79
#05347e		5, 52, 126

ANNEX IX PowerPoint Template

ANNEX X Deliverable Template

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable *x.x* <title>
<Dissemination level>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	Dx.x
Deliverable name	
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public/Confidential/EU restricted
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP1
Due date	
Version	
Actual submission date	<Filled in by the Coordinator>
Responsible organisation	
Editor(s)	
Contributor(s)	
Reviewer(s)	
Disclaimer	

DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	DD/MM/YY	Draft		Initial Draft
0.3	DD/MM/YY	Draft		Review
0.4	DD/MM/YY	Draft		Final review
1.0	DD/MM/YY	Final		Final approval and submission

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Summary

Standard text - "Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum."

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Introduction

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Subheading 1

"Sed ut perspiciatis unde omnis iste natus error sit voluptatem accusantium doloremque laudantium, totam rem aperiam, eaque ipsa quae ab illo inventore veritatis, et quasi architecto, beatae vitae dicta sunt explicabo."

Subheading 2

"Sed ut perspiciatis unde omnis iste natus error sit voluptatem accusantium doloremque laudantium, totam rem aperiam, eaque ipsa quae ab illo inventore veritatis, et quasi architecto, beatae vitae dicta sunt explicabo."

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DX-X <title>

Table 1 An table example

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4
Example	Example 2	- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. - Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.	Example: - Sitak ut, aliquip, provides benefits for LEAs - Sitak ut, aliquip, provides benefits for LEAs - Sitak ut, aliquip, provides benefits for LEAs

Conclusion
 Standard text - "Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum."

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